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**THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS IN THE STUDY OF THE
PHILOSOPHY OF CONFUCIUS AND SOCRATES**

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ABSTRACT

Studying the philosophical thoughts of Confucius and Socrates can be carried out by studying their texts and writings. For Confucius, the Analects was the most important text, recording his words, deeds, and doctrines. For Socrates, important texts include Plato's dialogues and the writings of Aristotle. By carefully analyzing these texts, one can understand their ideological perspectives and methodologies. This article is dedicated to theoretical and methodological basis in the study of the philosophy of Confucius and Socrates in the context of comparative studies.

Key words: Confucius, Socrates, comparative studies, humanism, kindness, ethical and moral system.

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**ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ
ФИЛОСОФИИ КОНФУЦИЯ И СОКРАТА****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Изучение философских мыслей Конфуция и Сократа можно осуществлять путем изучения их текстов и сочинений. Для Конфуция «Аналекты» были самым важным текстом, записывающим его слова, дела и доктрины. Для Сократа важными текстами являются диалоги Платона и сочинения Аристотеля. Тщательно анализируя эти тексты, можно понять их идеологические перспективы и методологии. Данная статья посвящена теоретико-методологическим основам изучения философии Конфуция и Сократа в контексте компаративистики.

Ключевые слова: Конфуций, Сократ, компаративистика, гуманизм, доброта, этико-нравственная система.

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KONFUTSIY VA SUQROT FALSAFASINI O'RGANISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI**ANNOTATSIYA**

Konfutsiy va Suqrotning falsafiy fikrlarini o'rganish ularning matnlari va yozuvlarini o'rganish orqali amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Konfutsiy uchun Analektlar uning so'zlari, ishlari va ta'limotlarini yozib olgan eng muhim matn edi. Suqrot uchun muhim matnlar Aflotunning dialoglari va Aristotelning asarlaridir. Bu matnlarni sinchiklab tahlil qilish orqali ularning mafkuraviy qarashlari va metodologiyasini tushunish mumkin. Ushbu maqola Konfutsiy va Suqrot falsafasini qiyosiy tadqiqotlar kontekstida o'rganishning nazariy va metodologik asoslariga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Konfutsiy, Suqrot, qiyosiy tadqiqotlar, insonparvarlik, mehr-oqibat, axloqiy-axloqiy tizim.

INTRODUCTION. Comparing the ideological views of Confucius and Socrates is the core of the study. You can explore their views on ethics, political philosophy, educational theory, etc. The focus of comparison can include their understanding and elaboration of concepts such as human nature, virtue, justice, and wisdom. At the same time, you can also analyze their thinking methods and reasoning methods, such as exploring their questioning skills, dialectical thinking and argumentation methods, etc.

LITERATURE REVIEW. Before them, ancient Greek and Chinese philosophers paid attention to the study and thinking of nature, that is, "Nature" as the object of observation and debate. Of course, their thinking of "Nature" is not what we now say as the sum of natural things and phenomena of the natural world, but specifically refers to the nature of things in motion change. Separated from the main body, it seems somewhat empty and impractical. Now when you trace the origins of humanism in Western philosophy, you usually trace it back to Socrates. To be sure, Socrates's former philosophers, such as Heraclitus and Demetrius, had plenty of aphorisms about the wisdom of life in the remnants of their writings, but Socrates was the founder of the first human philosophy, it was he who really moved Greek philosophy away from the natural philosophy and towards the study of people. The object of his study is no longer the nature, space or universe that natural philosophy studies, but the question of man, his thoughts, his morals, his sentiments, that is, the study of his spiritual self. In his opinion, we can not probe into the problem of human beings by the way of physical things, nor by empirical observation and logical analysis. Socrates pioneered Western philosophy's thinking about people. He believes that the purpose of philosophy is not the world of nature, but "Know yourself.". Socrates's philosophy focuses on morality. He was particularly interested in the topics "Character of virtue" and "What is good". He worked to invent a rational principle of right and wrong, and how to understand the meaning of morality. He wanted to set a reasonable standard for his life. These are questions about the nature of man.

According to the explanation by Zhang Zai, a Confucian of the Song Dynasty, Rixin refers to the way that has no boundaries and is endless. "Only newness day by day means great virtue. The principles are consistent, and then they are new day by day. With each passing day, there is still progress" (see "Zhang Zai Ji·Hengqu Yi Shuo")[1]. Dai Zhen, a scholar of the Qing Dynasty, pointed out when explaining "the metaphysics is called the Tao" in "Yi Zhuan": "The Tao is still walking. The qi changes and circulates, and it is endless, so it is called the Tao." (See "Mencius' Word Meanings", Vol.) This all means that the movement of heaven is endless and endless. In Confucian logic, the way of humanity is consistent with the way of heaven, so its fundamental spirit is eternal and endless. However, when we talk about "daily innovation", "progress" and "popularity", it also implies development, change, progress and renewal. Therefore, Tao has both a long-lasting and boundless side and a changing and renewing side. Therefore, while Dong Zhongshu, a Han Confucian, pointed out that "the great source of Tao comes from heaven, and if heaven does not change, Tao will not change", he also put forward the idea that "those who succeed in governing the world will have the same Tao, and those who succeed in troubled times will have their Tao change" and put forward the idea The political proposition of "changing political affairs" and "changing the

political system" (see "Book of Han·Biography of Dong Zhongshu·Countermeasures for Promoting Virtues").

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. The article uses the methods of comparative studies, analysis, synthesis, dialectical, organismic methods of scientific knowledge.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

Confucius's chief contribution to the Chinese philosophical tradition was that he was the first to consciously establish the spirit of reason in the moral sphere, representing the mainstream direction of the development of Confucianism, and has had the profound influence to the Chinese cultural tradition. Confucius was the first person in Chinese history to explore human value, human dignity and human status from the perspective of human beings, he created his own system of theories about man. Confucius's Confucianism also embodies humanism. Confucian ethics is rooted in human nature. Confucius's thought included the idea of "The unity of man and nature", which held that the universe and human relations were governed by the same moral order. Furthermore, Confucius's Confucian philosophy was essentially a practical philosophy of life, in which he wanted people to practice "Benevolence", "Righteousness", "Loyalty", "Forgiveness" and "Self-denial", take "Datong" as an ideal. He regarded the root of "Bad etiquette and music collapse" as People's moral decline, so the premise of "Resuming rites" was "Self-restraint", and "Resuming rites" was also "Benevolence". The core of Confucius's system is "Benevolence", which embodies Confucius's thought of human status, value and dignity, this is also a kind of humanism. As a requirement of self-discipline based on The Metaphysics of Morals, and as a criterion of regulating "The relationship between people", it undoubtedly has some significance to make people live in harmony. The Way to be a man is Confucius's thought on the cultivation and perfection of individual personality and morality. It is the foundation of Human's own development and the premise of realizing human's ultimate goal.

Before Socrates, the ancient Greek natural philosophy mainly established the rational spirit in the field of cognition, that is, rational cognition which tried to reason through logic, seek the universal origin of all things in the universe from the messy natural phenomena. Socrates began the transition from natural philosophy philosophy to humanistic philosophy, trying to pull Greek philosophy back from the sky to the earth, and thus explored various issues about human beings, society and ethics in depth in accordance with the spirit of reason. Socrates's ethics can also be said to be the ethics of the good and the supreme good. He agreed with the wisdom that "Philosophy should be the study of man", that the purpose of philosophy is not to know nature, but to "Know yourself". His ethics can be summed up in three sentences: all virtues are one; virtue is knowledge; and evil is caused by ignorance. The essence of these three sentences is: virtue is knowledge. He affirms that there is a general good, or the supreme good, above the concrete good. According to Socrates, goodness and virtue, however many and however different they may be, have a common nature which makes them virtues, and to answer the question of what is a virtue, it is better to focus on this common nature. While searching for the nature of good, Socrates also saw that concrete good and evil are relative. For all things are good to what they are good to, and evil to what they are not. From this, Socrates saw that the key was to make the right choice in the size of good and evil, and that required skill and knowledge. Thus the teleology of perfection evolved into the proposition that goodness is knowledge. Socrates further argued that good and evil should be justified by reason, and that only good becomes knowledge can it become good. In addition, Socrates's inquiry into the nature of things teaches us to "Know ourselves" rationally, which marks the beginning of the debate between rationalism and emotionalism. It is Socrates's fundamental idea of ethics to see knowledge as the foundation of morality.

Confucius, like Socrates, had a supreme quest, or the existence of truth, in their ethical systems of thought. Confucius repeatedly stressed the "Benevolence", represented by Confucius's Confucian thought, is from the human nature of good, developed a set of the most in line with human nature, human ethics. With benevolence as the core, Confucius also proposed a series of moral principles to be observed by everyone. The content of the moral norm system constructed by Confucianism with the principle of benevolence as the core is very rich, in addition to the above, Confucian also put

forward filial piety, fraternity, wide, sensitive, wisdom, thrift, respect, strong, Yi and other moral norms. In the whole system of Confucian moral norms, the spirit of "Benevolence" runs through all the time. It can be said that a series of Confucian moral norms are developed around the principle of benevolence. As a moral principle of Confucian ethics, benevolence starts from "Dear Love", but it is not limited to dear love, extend the term "Lover" to all members of society. In the ideal personality, the confucianists think that to achieve the perfect is to achieve "Saint inside and king outside". "The theme of philosophy is the way of the saint within and the king without, so it is not only to acquire this knowledge, but to develop this personality. Philosophy not only wants to know it, but also wants to experience it." The inner sage and outer king of Confucianism are the "Three programs" and "Eight items" of the university, that is, "The way of university, in the clear moral, in the people-friendly, in the best.". In accordance with the Confucian ancestor Confucius established the principle of "Similar in nature, far away from XI"[2] human nature, whether you are the son of heaven, or ordinary people, because of similar sex, so the day after tomorrow must be "Self-cultivation"-oriented. In the view of Confucianism, because of the nature of the decision, the sage must strengthen virtue cultivation, as a basis for the use of internal hair is the king outside.

As for the question of fate, some scholars think that Confucius adopted an evasive attitude, "How can we know death without knowing life?" In today's words, we still don't understand the truth of life, how can we know death? In the Shang dynasty, China adopted the religion of worshipping Heaven and earth. Confucius believed in the primitive Chinese concept of heaven as the ruler of the world and the deity of personality. Confucius thought that "Life and death have destiny, Wealth and honor in heaven", "Sin in heaven, no prayer also", "Do not know life, no gentleman," so he "Fear the fate of Heaven.". But he was not superstitious about Zhou's divination. He was also averse to ghosts. In Confucius's view, the question of life and death can not be discussed separately. If you want to understand death, you must first understand life. I believe that Confucius's "Unknown life, how do you know death", emphasizing the study of death by birth, the intention is not to avoid death, but it is to avoid the "Knowledge of death" into a few scholars to study the pure theoretical issues, and make it should be the ordinary people should strive to realize and implement the problem. This can be seen as another important feature of the social and practical character of Confucius's thoughts on death. But it cannot in any way constitute the theoretical basis for Confucius's disregard of death and his radical denial of the spiritual path of understanding that opposes life. And, indeed, Socrates, presumably content to be "Ignorant" of the nature of death, could not have done better.

Socrates believed in the immortality of the soul. But also to think that nature is indelible, and to emphasize the thinking of the self, fatalism is Socrates thinking about the people themselves, is also a result of his thinking. Socrates and Plato regarded philosophy as an activity of previewing death. Since ancient Greece, Western philosophy has a long metaphysical tradition, that is, it is committed to seeking and constructing a spiritual universe noumenon. The underlying motivation is to make the soul immortal in a sense, and the salvation of Christianity after death is also affected by it.

Their differences also reflect the differences between eastern and western philosophy. The core question of Westerners' life thinking is: why do people live? Or rather, what is the basis and significance of being alive? This is a question that a person poses to themselves when facing the universe, asking the ultimate basis and meaning of life. Therefore, the western Philosophy of life is essentially a philosophy of soul and a religion. The question that Chinese people are thinking about is: how to live? This is a question that a person poses to themselves when facing others, and it pursues the principles of properly handling interpersonal relationships. Therefore, China's Philosophy of life is essentially a moral philosophy and ethics.

The reality of ethics and morality is first of all the reality of self-consciousness in which thinking takes human beings as the object. In this way, as the reality of ethics and morality, it must initially be cognition and knowledge.

The ancient Chinese moral and ethical system is a moral humanistic theory that was laid down by Confucius, elaborated by Mencius and Xunzi, systematized by Confucians of the Han Dynasty, and ontologicalized by Confucianists of the Song and Ming dynasties. Confucian moral ethics is people-centered and cares about the eternal meaning of life. Its outlook on life and values emphasize

the authority of morality, the perfection of personality, the ethical order of family and society, and the common interests of social groups. Its core concept is "based on benevolence, "Using etiquette for practical purposes", its way of thinking and practical procedures are "inner sage and outer king", "respecting oneself and others" and then extending to society.

The moral and ethical ideological system of Confucianism contains three major aspects: virtue principles, ethical principles and self-cultivation principles. In this theoretical system, the principle of virtue is fundamental, the principle of ethics is applied, and the principle of self-cultivation is the practical bridge connecting morality, ethics, and politics. This constitutes the Confucianism based on "benevolence" and "ritual" is a trinity ideological system of morality, ethics, and politics that serves as the goal of life and takes "cultivation of oneself and peace of mind" as the goal of life.

The basic characteristics of the Confucian moral and ethical ideological system are firstly people-centered and moral "benevolence" as the basis, which has become a humanistic philosophy that establishes moral subjectivity. Although Confucius attached great importance to the role of "ritual", he deeply felt the importance of maintaining moral benevolence from the political reality of the collapse of etiquette and the lack of morality in the world at that time, and realized the truth that "the foundation of etiquette is benevolence". Therefore, he lamented, "If a person is not benevolent, what is etiquette? If a person is not benevolent, what is joy?" [3] When answering Lin Fang's question about "the foundation of etiquette," he exclaimed: "What a great question! Etiquette is not so extravagant." It is better to be frugal; to be mournful is to be sad than to be easy." ("The Analects of Confucius·Bayi") In this way, "ritual" as an external norm is directed to people's inner moral emotions, and this inner moral emotion is "Kindness to one's relatives." When he answered Duke Ai of Lu's question about politics, he clearly clarified the fundamental relationship between benevolence, righteousness, and etiquette, pointing out: "Government depends on people, taking people with their bodies, cultivating one's self with Tao, and cultivating Tao with benevolence. A benevolent person is a person who is loved by relatives." [4] Great; righteousness is appropriate, respecting the virtuous is great. Killing relatives (extremely), respecting the virtuous, etc., is born of etiquette." ("Book of Rites: Doctrine of the Mean") It can be seen that in the logic of Confucius' thought, politics is the center. Among people, the foundation of governance is to establish moral benevolence. Benevolence comes from family affection, and it is appropriate to respect the virtuous, while the norms of etiquette are based on morality. When Confucius answered Yan Yuan's question about benevolence, he pointed out: "Restraining oneself and restoring etiquette is benevolence. For one day to restrain oneself and return to etiquette, the world will return to benevolence. Benevolence depends on oneself, but not on others!" ("The Analects of Confucius·Yan Yuan") "Restore etiquette" Taking self-denial and self-cultivation as the premise, "self-denial" has the goal of conforming to the norms of etiquette and justice. The unity of internal cultivation, self-examination and external norms is benevolence, and the establishment of benevolence depends on people's own moral consciousness. These important thoughts of Confucius actually laid the foundation for the basic ideological model of Confucian "benevolence" characterized by "benevolence based on ritual and practical use". In this thought model, "benevolence" is the moral consciousness derived from human feelings (loving relatives and loving others), and is the internal basis for establishing the order of human ethics (propriety and justice), thereby establishing the subjective status of morality.

"Be benevolent to others" and "be benevolent to oneself". Confucianism after Confucius, especially Mencius and the Confucian scholars of the Song and Ming dynasties, generally established the Confucian moral and ethical ideological system based on Confucius's thinking. Even though Xunzi and Han Confucianism have different views on the good and evil of human nature and the relationship between benevolence and propriety, the fundamental issue discussed in their philosophy is still human, aiming to reveal the meaning and value of human existence between heaven and earth. , aims to cultivate a sound and perfect gentleman's personality, and aims to establish an ideal society that conforms to the spirit of benevolence and observes the order of human ethics.

Another feature of the Confucian moral and ethical ideological system is its emphasis on the daily updating of morals and the timely changes in etiquette. Confucius put forward the proposition that "Rixin is called virtue, and life is Yi" ("Book of Changes·Xici"). According to the explanation

by Zhang Zai, a Confucian of the Song Dynasty, Rixin refers to the way that has no boundaries and is endless. "Only newness day by day means great virtue. The principles are consistent, and then they are new day by day. With each passing day, there is still progress" (see "Zhang Zai Ji-Hengqu Yi Shuo"). Dai Zhen, a scholar of the Qing Dynasty, pointed out when explaining "the metaphysics is called the Tao" in "Yi Zhuan": "The Tao is still walking. The qi changes and circulates, and it is endless, so it is called the Tao." (See "Mencius' Word Meanings", Vol.) This all means that the movement of heaven is endless and endless. In Confucian logic, the way of humanity is consistent with the way of heaven, so its fundamental spirit is eternal and endless. However, when we talk about "daily innovation", "progress" and "popularity", it also implies development, change, progress and renewal. Therefore, Tao has both a long-lasting and boundless side and a changing and renewing side. Therefore, while Dong Zhongshu, a Han Confucian, pointed out that "the great source of Tao comes from heaven, and if heaven does not change, Tao will not change", he also put forward the idea that "those who succeed in governing the world will have the same Tao, and those who succeed in troubled times will have their Tao change" and put forward the idea The political proposition of "changing political affairs" and "changing the political system" (see "Book of Han·Biography of Dong Zhongshu·Countermeasures for Promoting Virtues"). Dong also elaborated on Confucius's subtle meaning in the "Spring and Autumn Annals: Bamboo Forest" chapter: "The way of "Spring and Autumn" is inherently subject to change, change is used for change, and it is often used for constant use... Therefore, those who say "Spring and Autumn" cannot be pacified. The ordinary meaning is doubtful and the great meaning is changed." Dong's thoughts and ideas are in line with Confucius' thoughts. "Book of Rites: The Doctrine of the Mean" quotes Confucius's words about "sincerity": "Therefore, sincerity is endless, and it will last forever." This "sincerity" is the way of "lasting and boundless"; it also says that "the virtue of nature is the combination of the outside and the inside." [5] "The way is the way to take measures at the right time." This "virtue of nature" is the way to change according to the times and adapt to the circumstances. In short, the Confucian way is not a rigid and unchanging way, but there are constant ways that are timeless and new, and there are also changing ways that are changing day by day. In the field of social and human affairs, what remains new over time is the fundamental spirit of morality and benevolence; what is ever-changing and new is the etiquette of adapting to the changing circumstances. Confucius had a lot to say about the changing nature of gains and losses in rituals over time. Confucius said in the chapter "The Analects of Confucius: Weizheng": "Because of the Xia rites, the gains and losses of the Yin can be known; the gains and losses of the Zhou due to the Yin rites can be known; those who may succeed the Zhou can be known for hundreds of generations." "Book of Rites· The book "Ritual Vessels" says: "Ritual is in line with the time of heaven, established in the earth's wealth, in compliance with ghosts and gods, in line with people's hearts, and in charge of all things. ...Li, time is the most important, and order follows." "Book of Rites" "Zhongni Yanju" chapter record says: "What is etiquette? It is the rule of affairs. A gentleman has his own affairs,...the system lies in etiquette, the text lies in etiquette, and the conduct of etiquette depends on people!" That is to say, etiquette depends on people! It adapts to current events, and its content and form change with the changes of the situation and personnel. In Yin Jixia and Zhou Jiyin, the content and form of the rituals all had profit and loss changes, so the profit and loss changes in subsequent generations can be imagined. In this case, Confucian moral ethics itself will inevitably change with the progress of the times. The words and deeds that stick to the old rituals and cling to the old rituals are also inconsistent with the revolutionary spirit of Confucian thought.

Another characteristic of Confucian moral and ethical thought is its distinct practicality. Confucius once put forward the standard of a gentleman to "cultivate oneself to bring peace to the people" ("The Analects of Confucius: Xian Wen"), and Mencius also put forward the ideal personality of "if you are poor, you can be good for yourself; if you are strong, you can be good for the world" ("Mencius: Devoting Your Heart"). The "Book of Rites·University" chapter talks about the succession of practicing sincerity and cultivating Qi and Zhiping, which actually establishes a complete thinking structure of moral-political practice based on self-cultivation and the end of governing the country and the world. Since then, Confucianism has gradually formed the ideological

and behavioral models of "inner sage and outer king" and "managing the world for practical purposes". True Confucianism in the past dynasties, from Confucius and Mencius in the pre-Qin Dynasty to Dong Zhongshu and Han Yu in the Han and Tang Dynasties, from Zhu Xi, Wang Yangming, and Liu Zongzhou in the Song and Ming Dynasties to Huang Zongxi, Gu Yanwu, and Wang Fuzhi in the Qing Dynasty, and even in modern times, Gong Zizhen, Tan Sitong, Kang Youwei, etc., are all true Confucians. Engage in moral practice and political practice according to this model very devoutly. Even though they suffered political setbacks and even suffered a bloody blow, their moral personality of "reading books and doing deeds of sages" and their practical spirit of practicing morality and martyrdom have not diminished a little. It can be said that they devoted themselves to death without giving up. This reflects the distinctive practical characteristics of Confucianism. This feature of Confucianism enables Confucian thinkers to develop their rational thinking closely around moral values and construct their ideological system, thus giving Confucian political philosophy a profound moral imprint.

The above-mentioned characteristics of Confucian moral and ethical thought determine the basic nature of the Confucian philosophical system: it is different from the Western intellectual philosophy tradition whose sole interest is seeking truth, and also different from the Western humanistic tradition that exalts the values of freedom, democracy, and human rights; it is both It is not an irrational religious philosophy, nor a purely rational ethical philosophy, but an Eastern humanistic philosophy that takes life as its main concern and the perfection of virtue as its highest value; what it values is the perfection of personal moral personality. , the orderliness of human relations and the morality of social politics. What is important is the practice of moral cultivation and the practice of social politics. Therefore, we can define Confucian moral and ethical thought as "practical moral metaphysics" and the entire Confucian philosophical system as "moral humanism."

The reason why Socrates enjoys such high praise is not only that the philosophical principles he pursued and adhered to changed the development direction of ancient Greek philosophy, thus causing a major turning point in the spirit itself - the individual subjective consciousness was confirmed and replaced the oracle. , and also because he incorporated ethics into philosophy, clearly stated that "virtue is knowledge", and became the founder of "subjective knowledge theory" in Western ethical and moral philosophy.

Socrates proposed a new philosophical principle in opposition to the Greek philosophy before him. This philosophical principle attributed the truth of objective things to consciousness or the thinking of the subject, thus making Greek philosophy shift from seeking outside the heart to seeking within the heart. Before Socrates, most natural philosophers explained the generation and existence of things from the origin of the world, and attributed the origin of the world to water, fire, atoms, etc. Socrates believed that the various principles advocated by natural philosophers could not explain the causes of things at all, nor were they sufficient to explain the coordination and unity of the world. Finally he discovered the germ of truth in the philosophy of Anaxagoras and was deeply inspired. Anaxagoras not only proposed that seeds are the origin of all things in the world, but also proposed the principle that the driving force behind seeds forming all things in the world is the mind. Although Anaxagoras still did not completely get rid of the relics of natural philosophy when explaining the generation and existence of all things in the world, his philosophical significance lies in proposing the mind and investigating the thought itself. In Anaxagoras, "thought is represented as an omnipotent concept, as a negative power that governs all specific things and entities; its movement is the dissolution of all consciousness." [6] Socrates adopted Anaxagoras' principle that the mind is a ruling, real and self-determining universal. To this end, he gives up a certain sense and turns to the heart, where he seeks the truth of existence. In his view, when people pursue the true cause and truth of things, they cannot seek external verification based on the senses, but should reflect within themselves to reach the truth of existence. Socrates believed that the reason why philosophers in the past did not grasp the truth of existence was that the former philosophers looked outward and always tried to obtain the truth from the existence of external things. In fact, the basic principle of philosophy is to know oneself and return to oneself. Man's vocation and purpose, the ultimate goal and truth of the

world, and everything that exists in and of itself must be achieved through man himself. Therefore, truth is "knowing you" Own".

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS.

The core of moral philosophy is cognition and knowledge, that is, cognition and knowledge of the good are overriding. "Virtue is knowledge" succinctly highlights the ethical and moral thought of Socrates' epistemology. Socrates was not concerned with nature but with human affairs. In his opinion, all kinds of science are of no benefit to human life, so what he should care about is things related to human moral nature, so that people can do the greatest good and know the most true things. Therefore, he is neither like the natural philosophers who always argue about the nature of things, nor like the wise men who explore how the things in the world are produced, what laws are responsible for the things in the sky, etc. The problem. He preferred to "discuss from time to time matters concerning mankind, and study and study what is pious and what is impious; what is fitting and what is unfit; what is just and what is unjust; what is What is wise and what is unwise; what is resolute and what is cowardly; what is the basis of governing a country, what are the qualities of a person who is good at governing people; and other topics." Therefore, the essence and goal of his philosophy is not to establish a natural philosophy system, but to inspire people to love truth and virtue in order to transform personal behavior into a behavior of universal significance. To this end, he often goes to markets, squares and other places where people gather, and talks to everyone in Attica's elegant manner, guiding people to think about their responsibilities, helping people care about their ethics, awakening people's moral consciousness, and making people think. And understand what is legitimate, what are universal principles, what is truth and beauty in itself; make people aware and convinced that they have truth and goodness in their own thoughts, and have the potential to produce moral behavior and understand the truth, so as to Enable people to live a decent life. For Socrates, possessing virtue and living a right life lies first in knowing virtue.

CONCLUSION.

Socrates guided the knowledge of good and virtue to the inner pursuit of the subject. On the one hand, it revealed the buds of self-realization in the history of Western philosophy; on the other hand, it also highlighted the principle of subject freedom. In summary, Socrates' moral philosophy has three basic characteristics: First, morality is not a skill, it involves the principle issue of why people are human beings, that is, the principle issue of whether human will is reasonable or not, and whether it should or should not be done. Morality is inherent in people, and the standard of good and evil lies with people themselves. Second, the source of morality lies in the person himself, because good is intrinsic rather than external. However, Socrates also believed that good is knowable, and knowledge about what a person is doing can be taught, that is, it can inspire people to realize themselves. Be aware of what is inherent in human beings. Since the good and evil of people are inherent in everyone's spiritual nature, then people should treat people themselves according to what is consistent with themselves. Third, the significance of moral philosophy lies in the fact that provisions such as goodness, ethics, and justice are freely established by the subject himself through cognition. The reason why people are free lies in the fact that they do not seek anything from outside. It lies in the fact that consciousness creates something real from itself, and also produces the good as an end. Therefore, morality is self-satisfaction. If a person can turn himself into a moral person, he will gain others through knowledge of morality, that is, he will realize his own nature through self-reflection, which is consistent with his own nature and consistent with his own nature. The person who conforms to the essence is free.

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МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕССАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ

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ЁШЛАРИ ОНГИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-МАДАНИЙ ВА АКСИОЛОГИК АСОСЛАРИ” НОМЛИ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬ
ЛОЙИҲА ДОИРАСИДА НАШРГА ТАЙЁРЛАНГАН.

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